

Online Appendix

Table A.1. List of sample countries

Afghanistan	Colombia	Iceland	Morocco	Slovakia
Albania	Congo	India	Mozambique	Slovenia
Algeria	Costa Rica	Indonesia	Myanmar	South Africa
Argentina	Cote d'Ivoire	Iran	Nepal	Spain
Armenia	Croatia	Iraq	Netherlands	Sri Lanka
Australia	Cyprus	Ireland	New Zealand	Sweden
Austria	Czechia	Israel	Nicaragua	Switzerland
Azerbaijan	Denmark	Italy	Niger	Tajikistan
Bahrain	Dominican Rep.	Japan	Nigeria	Tanzania
Bangladesh	Ecuador	Jordan	Norway	Thailand
Belarus	Egypt	Kazakhstan	Pakistan	Togo
Belgium	El Salvador	Kenya	Panama	Tunisia
Benin	Estonia	Kyrgyzstan	Paraguay	Turkiye
Bolivia	Ethiopia	Latvia	Peru	Turkmenistan
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Finland	Lebanon	Philippines	Uganda
Botswana	France	Lithuania	Poland	Ukraine
Brazil	Gabon	Luxembourg	Portugal	United Arab Emirates
Bulgaria	Georgia	Madagascar	Romania	United Kingdom
Burkina Faso	Germany	Malawi	Russia	United States
Cambodia	Ghana	Malaysia	Rwanda	Uruguay
Cameroon	Greece	Mali	Saudi Arabia	Uzbekistan
Canada	Guatemala	Mauritania	Senegal	Venezuela
Chad	Guinea	Mexico	Serbia	Vietnam
Chile	Honduras	Moldova	Sierra Leone	Zambia
China	Hungary	Mongolia	Singapore	Zimbabwe

Table A.2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Dependent variable					
Life ladder	1807	5.530	1.127	2.179	8.019
Happiness 2	1869	3.783	0.976	0.830	6.875
Interest variables					
Political constraint III	1998	0.291	0.233	0	0.716
Political constraint V	1997	0.420	0.354	0	0.891
Checks and balances	1806	3.147	1.540	1	17
Opposition vote share	1860	20.283	22.956	0	99.5
Baseline control variables					

Real GDP, ppp	2000	24207.87	23928.83	1024.729	139678
Inflation	1954	5.585	16.722	-10.067	557.201
Population growth	2000	1.313	1.474	-4.257	18.128
Unemployment rate	1998	7.174	4.959	0.14	31.11
Education	2000	2.063	0.531	-0.023	2.657
Natural resources rent	1986	0.560	2.142	-9.142	4.154
Additional control variables					
Political stability	2000	-0.178	0.917	-2.826	1.620
Democracy	1576	6.222	3.664	0	10
Legal quality	1952	5.482	1.761	1.980	9.210
Channels					
Political freedom	1999	61.468	28.041	1	100
Economic freedom	1952	6.727	1.064	2.52	8.84
Income inequality	2000	41.791	10.288	15.163	72.892
Control of corruption	2000	-0.037	1.043	-1.672	2.459
Rule of law	2000	-0.027	1.011	-2.333	2.125
Unemployment	1998	7.174	4.959	0.140	31.110

Source: authors' calculations.

Table A.3. Balancing quality

	Political constraints as the treatment variable	
	Before Balancing	After Balancing
R-squared	0.226	0.000
F-statistic	111.444	0.000
P-value	0.001	1.000

Notes: These results are drawn from a (weighted) regression of the treatment variable on the covariates. The treatment variable is “political constraints”, and the set of covariates includes GDP per capita, consumer price index, total natural resources rent, and unemployment rate.

Table A.4. Impact of political constraints on happiness (r=1)

VARIABLES	Outcome variable: Happiness							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Political Constraints	0.305*	0.452***	0.302*	0.450***	0.368***	0.465***	0.373***	0.467***
	(0.162)	(0.173)	(0.162)	(0.172)	(0.083)	(0.084)	(0.083)	(0.084)
Bootstrap in the 1st step	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500
Covariates in the 2nd step	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE in the 2nd step	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Country FE in the 2nd step	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.003	0.025	0.004	0.025	0.667	0.685	0.669	0.688
Observations	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640

Notes: Heteroskedasticity-robust (Huber–White) standard errors are reported in parentheses. (***; **; *) indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. All covariates are lagged by one period, relative to the treatment variable.

Table A.5. Impact of political constraints on happiness (r=3)

VARIABLES	Outcome variable: Happiness							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Political Constraints	0.341**	0.454***	0.348**	0.462***	0.400***	0.475***	0.406***	0.479***
	(0.161)	(0.171)	(0.161)	(0.170)	(0.084)	(0.087)	(0.085)	(0.087)
Bootstrap in the 1st step	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500
Covariates in the 2nd step	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE in the 2nd step	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Country FE in the 2nd step	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.005	0.022	0.006	0.023	0.659	0.674	0.661	0.677
Observations	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640	1,640

Notes: Heteroskedasticity-robust (Huber–White) standard errors are reported in parentheses. (***; **; *) indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. All covariates are lagged by one period, relative to the treatment variable.

Table A.6. Robustness checks: unobserved confounders

	Without controls	Baseline controls	Adding additional controls
Baseline coefficients (β) (OLS)	0.997***	0.270***	0.26***
Oster's bounds ($\beta, \beta^* \{ \text{Min } 1, 1.3R^2 \} \delta = 1$)	[0.99, 10.29]	[0.27, 10.73]	[0.26, 10.38]
Delta (δ) statistic for $\beta = 0$	2.074 > 1	2.10 > 1	3.11 > 1
Rmax Value	0.60	0.80	0.80
Regions dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table A.7. OLS Regressions

VARIABLES	Dependent variable: Happiness					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Political constraints V	0.907*** (0.047)	0.175*** (0.046)				
Checks and balance			0.138*** (0.017)	0.066*** (0.008)		
Opposition vote share					0.008*** (0.001)	0.002*** (0.000)
Constant	5.139*** (0.020)	1.318*** (0.431)	5.103*** (0.054)	1.073** (0.443)	5.365*** (0.013)	0.778* (0.399)
Main controls	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,804	1,735	1,634	1,582	1,682	1,619
Adjusted R ²	0.481	0.757	0.451	0.763	0.438	0.757

Notes: Heteroskedasticity-robust (Huber–White) standard errors are reported in parentheses. (***, **, *) indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Table A.8. OLS Regressions

VARIABLES	Dependent variable: Happiness2					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Political constraints V	0.426*** (0.036)	0.313*** (0.033)				
Checks and balance			0.078*** (0.011)	0.076*** (0.012)		
Opposition vote share					0.007*** (0.000)	0.006*** (0.000)
Constant	3.601*** (0.015)	6.087*** (0.250)	3.549*** (0.033)	6.144*** (0.345)	3.650*** (0.009)	5.605*** (0.256)
Main controls	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,866	1,792	1,678	1,624	1,730	1,663
Adjusted R ²	0.397	0.423	0.409	0.441	0.408	0.435

Notes: Heteroskedasticity-robust (Huber–White) standard errors are reported in parentheses. (***, **, *) indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Table A.9. GMM estimates

VARIABLES	Dependent variable: Happiness					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
L.Happiness	0.609*** (0.058)	0.611*** (0.062)	0.706*** (0.062)	0.607*** (0.061)	0.624*** (0.060)	0.610*** (0.048)
Political constraints V	0.157*** (0.059)	0.345*** (0.131)				
Checks and balance			0.033*** (0.011)	0.036*** (0.013)		
Opposition vote share					0.002*** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.001)
Constant	0.529** (0.209)	0.533** (0.259)	0.237 (0.220)	1.293*** (0.445)	0.364* (0.216)	0.329 (0.360)
Main controls	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,397	1,176	1,315	1,17	1,432	1,02
Countries	121	117	121	117	121	117
Instruments	23	45	25	43	21	43
AR (1) P-value	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.002
AR (2) P-value	0.865	0.286	0.663	0.392	0.625	0.382
Hansen P-value	0.346	0.323	0.125	0.377	0.649	0.546

Notes: Two-step system GMM estimates are reported. Standard errors are heteroskedasticity-robust two-step standard errors corrected using the Windmeijer (2005) finite-sample adjustment and are shown in brackets. ***, **, * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. L denotes the lag operator.

Table A.10. GMM estimates

VARIABLES	Dependent variable: Happiness2					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
L.Happiness2	0.699*** (0.069)	0.787*** (0.112)	0.673*** (0.063)	0.891*** (0.053)	0.722*** (0.068)	0.823*** (0.069)
Political constraints V	0.185*** (0.069)	0.392*** (0.137)				
Checks and balance			0.020*** (0.007)	0.018*** (0.007)		
Opposition vote share					0.002*** (0.001)	0.007*** (0.002)
Constant	-0.178 (0.389)	0.452 (0.424)	0.141 (0.360)	1.014*** (0.360)	1.064*** (0.331)	0.363 (0.436)
Main controls	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,488	1,195	1,42	1,167	1,526	703
Countries	121	117	121	117	121	67
Instruments	26	29	25	31	15	35
AR (1) P-value	0.000	0.002	0.005	0.008	0.000	0.001
AR (2) P-value	0.482	0.138	0.325	0.245	0.374	0.241
Hansen P-value	0.653	0.188	0.536	0.365	0.216	0.424

Notes: Two-step system GMM estimates are reported. Standard errors are heteroskedasticity-robust two-step standard errors corrected using the Windmeijer (2005) finite-sample adjustment and are shown in brackets. ***, **, * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. L denotes the lag operator.

Figure A.1. Correlation between political constraint and happiness

Source: authors' construction

Figure A.2. Dose-response function of the effect of political constraint on happiness

Notes: This graph shows the estimated dose-response function (DRF) between political constraints and happiness based on EBCT regression. The shaded grey areas represent 95% normal confidence intervals of the DRF based on bootstrapped standard errors obtained using $R = 500$ replications.